

HaloBase: development of database system for halophilic bacteria and archaea with respect to proteomics, genomics & other molecular traits

Hetal Ukani¹, Megha K Purohit¹, John J George², Sneha Paul² and Satya P Singh^{1*}

¹ Department of Biosciences, Saurashtra University, Rajkot 360 005, India

² Department of Bioinformatics, Christ College, Vidya Niketan, Rajkot 360 005, India

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This study presents HaloBase, a specialized genome database for halophilic bacteria and archaea, which covers molecular aspects and diversity based studies. In HaloBase, 23 organisms were selected and integrated their detailed information consisting more than 55,000 genes, about 50,000 proteins with the functionality to view its 3D structure and about 1,000 structural RNAs. The database, available at <http://halobase.info>, will provide a platform for storage and analysis of halophiles for research and commercial purposes.

Keywords: Data base, Genome, Halophiles, Microsoft access, Proteins

Introduction

Extremophiles, in general, hold secret about the molecular evolution of life and are being explored from both microbial diversity and biotechnological standpoint^{1,2}. Halophilic microbes are one of the most widely studied groups of extremophiles. Over the years, authors have been involved with the halophilic/haloalkaliphilic bacteria from saline habitats of coastal Gujarat, exploring diversity, phylogeny, enzymatic profiling and properties of extracellular enzymes³⁻¹⁰. In addition to haloalkaliphilic bacteria, salt-tolerant alkaliphilic actinomycetes are also being explored with respect to their diversity and biotechnological potential¹¹⁻¹⁶. In recent years, attention is being focused on the entire community of ecological niche using metagenomic approaches¹⁷⁻²⁰. This study presents creation of HaloBase database system for halophilic bacteria and archaea, which would be useful to researchers working in microbiology and molecular biology focusing on genes and proteins. HaloBase reflects exhaustive diversity and functional analysis of saline system.

Methodology

HaloBase contains range of information about genes, proteins, RNAs, genome sequence, protein structure,

proteomics and genomics. The database also facilitates easy search on the functionality of data with wide search criteria. It was constructed in Microsoft Access 2007 (<http://office.microsoft.com/en-gb/access/default.aspx>) for the easy access and portability. Halophilic bacteria and archaea were selected for inclusion of HaloBase. The backend database was created in Microsoft Access and front end was done in ASP (<http://msdn.microsoft.com/en-us/library/aa286483.aspx>), which provided easy web access to database for data entry, retrieval and analysis. Data was collected from the various publicly available databases [NCBI (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov), PDB (www.pdb.org) and GOLD (<http://genomesonline.org>)].

Data Input

In HaloBase, 23 organisms (Table. 1) were selected and integrated their detailed information consisting of more than 55,000 genes, about 50,000 proteins with the functionality to view their 3D structures and about 1,000 structural RNAs. Whole genome sequence was also collected in 5 different formats for the selected organism under study. It also included functionality to add and edit data to the database through a user friendly web based portal facilitating researchers to update and maintain database system as per their new research and findings. Major aspects taken into consideration are habitat characteristics, biocatalytic potential, salinity and molecular properties, proteomics and genomics. Whole

* Author for correspondence

E-mail: satyapsingh@yahoo.com; satyapsingh125@gmail.com

Table.1—List of halophilic bacteria and archaea included in HaloBase

No.	Organism name	Function	Kingdom	Group	Genome Seq. Status
1	<i>Alkaliphilus metalliredigens</i> QYMF	An alkiphilic, moderately halophilic metal-reducing bacterium isolated from borax leachate ponds	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Complete
2	<i>Bacillus halodurans</i> C-125	Alkaliphilic organism used in the industrial production of -galactosidase and xylanase	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Complete
3	<i>Candidatus Chlorothrix halophila</i>	Halophilic phototroph	Bacteria	Chloroflexi	Inprogress
4	<i>Hahella chejuensis</i> KCTC 2396	Exopolysaccharide-producing slightly halophilic bacterium	Bacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Complete
5	<i>Haloarcula marismortui</i> ATCC 43049	Haloarcula marismortui ATCC 43049	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Complete
6	<i>Halobacterium salinarum</i>	Chemoheterotrophic obligate extreme halophilic archeon	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Inprogress
7	<i>Halobacterium</i> sp. NRC-1	Chemoheterotrophic obligate extreme halophilic archeon	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Complete
8	<i>Halobaculum gomorrense</i>	Extreme halophilic isolated from dead Sea	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Inprogress
9	<i>Halobiforma lacisalsi</i> AJ5	Extremely halophilic archaeal	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Inprogress
10	<i>Haloferax volcanii</i> DS 2	Halophilic organism isolated from the dead Sea	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Inprogress
11	<i>Halogeometricum borinense</i> DSM 11551	Halophilic bacterium	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Inprogress
12	<i>Halorhodospira halophila</i> SL1	Sulfur-oxidizing extreme halophile	Bacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Complete
13	<i>Halorubrum lacusprofundi</i>	Extremely halophilic archaeon isolated from the Antarctic	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Inprogress
14	<i>Halorubrum lacusprofundi</i> ATCC 49239	Extremely halophilic archaeon isolated from the Antarctic	Archaea	Eukaryota	Draft Assembly
15	<i>Halothermothrix orenii</i> H 168	Thermophilic halophile	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Draft Assembly
16	<i>Marinobacter aquaeolei</i> VT8	Moderately halophilic hydrocarbon-degrading bacterium	Bacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Complete
17	<i>Methanococcoides burtonii</i> DSM 6242	Psychrotolerant methanogenic archeon	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Complete
18	<i>Methylophaga thalassica</i>	Halophilic methylotroph	Bacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Inprogress
19	<i>Natranaerobius thermophilus</i> JW/NM-WN-LF	A haloalkalithermophilic bacterium.	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Inprogress
20	<i>Natrialba asiatica</i>	Non-pigmented halophile	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Inprogress
21	<i>Oceanobacillus iheyensis</i> HTE831	Extremely halotolerant bacterium.	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Complete
22	<i>Salinibacter ruber</i> DSM 13855	Extremely halophilic, strictly aerobic, red-pigmented bacterium	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes/Chlorobi	Complete
23	<i>Vibrio campbellii</i> AND4	Halophilic marine bacterium	Bacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Draft Assembly

genome sequence is available for both reference sequence and GenBank sequence in 5 different display formats (GenBank, FASTA, ASN.1, Brief and Summary). Database allowed visualization of 3D structures of protein by submitting amino acid sequence to Mofit 3D.

BLAST Functionality

BLAST programs are widely used tools for searching protein and DNA databases for sequence

similarities²¹. It is a heuristic that attempts to optimize a specific similarity measure. In HaloBase, Perl Script was used to develop a BLAST search program for DNA or Protein against NCBI database.

Retrieval of Data

HaloBase database provides easy access, retrieval and manipulation from ASP pages using SQL queries for the data selection from the database based

Fig. 1— a) Snapshot of HaloBase (Home page of created database displays brief information of database and affiliation of authors and a guide for database search and creation); b) Data access by selecting 'Genome Project' (A feature which allows user to access data by its organism name and other taxonomic classification)

on type search (genome project, organism name, function, kingdom, genome sequence in GenBank, FASTA, ASN.1, brief and summary formats, gene, protein and RNA) by the name of organism, product, gene, PID and general name.

Results and Discussion

Constructed database included nearly all information on the most widely studied and reported halophilic bacteria and archaea. In this data base, major aspects incorporated were primarily physiological and molecular

Fig. 2—a) Snapshot of displayed organism details (database facilitates user by giving detail description of selected halophilic bacteria/archaea e.g. *Candidatus Chlorothrix halophila*); b) Detailed list of Gene could be retrieved by using Halobase e.g. *Bacillus halodurans C-125*

3a

Motif3D - a java protein structure viewer

Search Results

Structures Available for the Submitted Sequence:

A BLAST search of the Protein Data Bank has been performed.

The following list shows the structures most closely matching your query sequence. Please note that they may have varying degrees of similarity to your query sequence (as indicated by the % identity) and do not necessarily represent the same protein.

Click on a "View Structure" link to launch Motif3D without a fingerprint or select "Find Fingerprints" to retrieve any fingerprints that can be shown on the selected structure:

Structure	E Value	% Identity	View Structure	Find Fingerprints
1is2 (PDB description)	4.6	19%	View Structure	Find Fingerprints
1f9u (PDB description)	6.0	23%	View Structure	Find Fingerprints
1e4g (PDB description)	6.0	26%	View Structure	Find Fingerprints
1bg4 (PDB description)	6.0	27%	View Structure	Find Fingerprints
1b3z (PDB description)	6.0	27%	View Structure	Find Fingerprints
1b3y (PDB description)	6.0	27%	View Structure	Find Fingerprints
1b3x (PDB description)	6.0	27%	View Structure	Find Fingerprints
1b3w (PDB description)	6.0	27%	View Structure	Find Fingerprints

3b

Motif3D - a java protein structure viewer

Applet launched with PDB code 1B3Z...

been designed specifically for use with the PRINTS database. Through selecting a PDB structure that corresponds to a print can be visualised. The viewer also allows manual highlighting of motifs of interest on the structure, together with other

Examples of viewer in use:

1) Motifs of the GPCRHHDDOPSH fingerprint shown on the structure of bovine rhodopsin (1B3Z)

Java Applet Window

- Selecting 'Quit' from the menu will exit the viewer.

View menu

- Selecting 'Background' from the View menu displays the structure on a white instead of a black background. This may be particularly useful if the image is to be printed.

FingerPRINTScan information Window

The FingerPRINTScan program allows PRINTS and prePRINTS motifs to be shown on the structure. Information will appear here each time the program is run.

Fig. 3—a) 3D structure view; b) Motif3D search for similar structure

properties, required by researchers for the study of halophilic organisms.

HaloBase is a specialized database for halophilic organisms, which includes halophilic bacteria & archaea (Fig. 1a). HaloBase also includes functionality to add and edit data to the database through a user friendly web based portal facilitating researchers to update and maintain database system. Access to the data could also be done in easier way by selecting 'Genome Project'. This feature allows users to access data by its organism

name and other taxonomic classification (Fig. 1b). Genome sequence is available for both, Reference Sequence and GenBank Sequence in 5 different formats (GenBank, FASTA, ASN1, Brief and Summary). The search for particular specific details for organism is added feature, which will facilitates users by giving detail description of selected halophilic bacteria/archaea. This will also allow getting insight into the list of genes, proteins, and RNA sequences and features, which are already studied and submitted to publically funded databases (Fig. 2).

Major advantages of HaloBase over other databases include filter option form on main page and detailed page to filter records according to the need, and easy access and retrieval of data from the database. HaloBase contains detailed information on 55000 genes, about 50000 proteins with the facility to view its 3D structure and 1000 structural RNAs. It would be a specialized publicly available database on halophilic organisms with functionality to view 3D structure and Motif3D search for similar structures (Fig. 3). Functionality to add and edit data to the database through a user friendly web based portal facilitates researchers to update and maintain database.

Conclusions

HaloBase database that included molecular aspects required for the study of halophilic organisms is expected to provide easy access to wide range of information and assist in data storage, comparison and analysis.

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